

EFFECT OF PLY ORIENTATION ON STIFFNESS REDUCTION OF Gr/BMI COMPOSITES DURING COMPRESSION CYCLING

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ABSTRACT

Stiffness changes during low frequency compression cycling were measured for Gr/BMI composite plates of varying ply orientations. A multiple sample compression cycling test system was used which gave continuous strain data over a three months period. Degradation was minimal at 25°C but significant at 149°C at loads of about 10% of the compressive strength. Fiber microbuckling, kinking, and matrix shear cracking were observed. Analysis of failure surfaces, quadratic ply failure criteria and delamination propensity indicated stiffness degradation was minimum with minimum tensile strain on 90° plies, maximum axial strain capability, minimum (+45/-45) interfaces, and maximum critical interlaminar shear stress.

INTRODUCTION

Aircrafts hub and wings are subject to compressive loads in service and a comprehensive understanding of compression creep and fatigue of composites is crucial to the successful implementation of future high speed supersonic aircraft (e.g. the HSCT). Unfortunately, the behavior of CFRP in compression is still less thoroughly understood than their behavior in tension. Compression cycling of composites is therefore needed to verify models for the prediction of long term strength [1], fatigue and creep [2], and aging effects. Evidence of nonlinear compression behavior of composite [3] suggests that high frequency fatigue data cannot be extrapolated to lower frequencies, such as a typical HSCT schedule. A unique multiple sample test system with controlled temperature/moisture capability was calibrated [4], and used in this work to study the stiffness reduction in different ply orientations of quasi-isotropic layups of graphite/bismaleimide composites. Previous work with tensile loading showed that Gr/BMI is more fatigue resistant than epoxy and has excellent high temperature (250°C) properties [5,6].

BACKGROUND

Decreases in stiffness due to tensile loading have been correlated with increases in crack density and delamination area [7-9]. Damage mechanics models typically use a damage parameter D which increases from 0 to 1 as the stiffness decreases from its initial value E_0 . Various models [9-11], notably based on damage strain energy release rate [12,13] relate D to the number of loading cycles N , and have a form which models a Paris-type phenomenological propagation law:

$$\frac{dD}{dN} = f(\text{loading, environment}) \cdot D^B \quad (1)$$

This general relation does not specify damage modes, which in compression may include delamination, fiber breaks, kinking, debonding or microbuckling and matrix cracking [14-16]. Other factors to be considered in compression include initial fiber waviness, the possibility for plate buckling and the sample crushing at the end of the test. Stress and/or thermal cycling further opens the possibility of mixed, synergistic or changing failure mechanisms. Delamination is considered to be the most prevalent life-limiting mode of damage under compressive cyclical loading [17], but little experimental work has been reported in this area. Komorowski *et al* [16] carried out cyclical loading which indicated that stacking sequence affects the fatigue life of laminates even more significantly than the choice of materials system.

EXPERIMENTAL

The specimens tested in compression cycling were 16-ply layups of IM7/5260-H Gr/BMI including unidirectional (0°, 90°), bidirectional (+45°/-45°), and four quasi-isotropic layups: A ([+45/0/-45/90]_{2s}), B ([+45/-45/0/90]_{2s}), C ([+45/-45/0/+45/-45/90/+45/-45]_s), and D ([90/+45/0/-45/0/0/+45/0]_s). In addition, IITRI type specimens g (0°), i (90°), and k (quasi-isotropic A) were cycled and subsequently tested to failure in static compression to investigate residual strengths. Specimen geometry is given in Figure 1, and specimen dimensions are given in Table 1.

Figure 1. Specimens geometry (drawings not to scale)

Table 1. Specimens dimensions

Specimens	Total length with tabs (m)	Length (m) (without tabs)	Thickness with tabs (m)	Thickness without tabs (m)	Width (m)
A, B, C, D	0.254	0.151	0.005	0.002	0.0254
g, i, k	0.091	0.005	0.005	0.002	0.0127

Specimens were cycled with a five hour period: four hours loading at 25°C or 149°C at 10% of the initial high temperature compressive strength followed by one hour active cooling with no load. A unique multiple sample test system with controlled load/temperature/moisture capability was used to cycle samples up to three months [1, 4].

RESULTS

Figure 2 shows a typical strain-time output plotted for selected cycles. Elastic stiffnesses were computed from the instantaneous unloading strains on each cycle. Measured strains varied 2% to 15% between gages on opposite sides of the samples, but stiffness trends were the same in all cases. At room temperature, E(N) changed little for 90° samples but there were indications of a slow decrease for +/-45° samples after a slight initial increase. Limited data on cyclic compression of 0° layups showed a 30% stiffness reduction after 250 cycles at 25°C. Figure 3 shows typical normalized stiffness changes for the quasi-A layup during room temperature cycling. Figure 4 shows stiffness data during cycling at 149°C. After 465 cycles, the stiffness

Figure 2. Selected 5 hour creep cycles at 149°C, $\sigma_x = -76$ MPa, Sample A22

Figure 3. Compressive modulus (quasi-isotropic samples) under cyclic loading at 25°C

decreased to 93% of the original stiffness for layup B, 89% for layup A, 84% for layup D, and 80% for layup C. Similar trends occurred when measuring loading strains. Higher loads were found to give short term increases before similar stiffness during the first month or two. Most showed later evidence of axial restriction by the clamping bolts holding the plates needed to prevent buckling. All intact samples were given standard compression or tensile failure tests at 25°C before and after the three months cycling at 149°C. IITRI specimens exhibited various failure patterns depending on their ply layup. Following standard nomenclature [18], the following observations could be made: Irrespective of their loading history (as-received, cycled at room temperature, cycled at high temperature), all specimens with the same layup failed in the same mode. Unidirectional 0° specimens (g) failed in the transverse mode, i.e. with a fracture surface parallel to the thickness direction but oriented at an angle of 10° to 20° in the width direction.

Figure 4. Compressive modulus (quasi-isotropic samples) under cyclic loading at 149°C

Unidirectional 90° specimens (i) failed in the shear mode, i.e. with a fracture surface at an angle to the specimen width. The orientation of the fracture surface was however not 45° but consistently 60°. Quasi-isotropic (A) specimens failed in a combination of brooming (splitting of the plies in the thickness direction) and shear modes. Even though the fiber glass tabs were tapered, fracture surfaces often initiated at the tab ends.

ANALYSIS

Comparison of Figures 3 and 4 indicates that coupled thermal and mechanical fatigue accounts for a general reduction in stiffness. Analyses of ply orientation effects on stiffness reduction were carried out by considering a) sample bending on compression behavior, b) failure modes, c) ply stresses and ply strength ratios, and d) relative interlaminar shear stresses.

EFFECT OF BENDING ON COMPRESSION BEHAVIOR

Laminate plate analysis was carried out to assess the stresses in the various plies during compression cycling. The differing ultimate tensile and compressive properties were handled by designating the plies in tension (the 90° plies) as a different material than those in compression. Ply properties after one cycle to 149°C are given in Table 2.

It was shown that the bending moment needed to impart the maximum possible curvature ($k_1 = 4.36 \cdot 10^{-3}$) was only about $1.2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ MN and this had typically 1% or less effect on all ply stresses. This moment may be caused by partial plate bending due to the tolerances of the shims clamping both sides of the samples between the side plates. (The shims fill the thickness added to the sample ends by the fiberglass tabs needed for subsequent static testing).

Table 2. Properties of the Gr/BMI ply.

Property	Fiber direction (0°)	Transverse direction (90°)
Tensile modulus (Pa)	$E_x = 1.49 \cdot 10^{11}$	$E_y = 8.75 \cdot 10^9$
Compressive modulus (Pa)	$E'_x = 6.1 \cdot 10^{10}$	$E'_y = 1.1 \cdot 10^{10}$
Shear modulus (Pa)	$E_s = 4.34 \cdot 10^9$	
Tensile strength (Pa)	$X = 2.14 \cdot 10^9$	$Y = 7.5 \cdot 10^7$
Compressive strength (Pa)	$X' = 1.78 \cdot 10^9$	$Y' = 2.93 \cdot 10^8$
Shear strength (Pa)	$S = 1.63 \cdot 10^8$	
Thermal expansion (°C ⁻¹)	$\alpha_x = -0.09 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$\alpha_y = 40 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{12} = 0.279$	
Ply thickness (m)	$t = 147 \cdot 10^{-6}$	
Density (kg.m ⁻³)	$\rho = 1.8$	

ANALYSIS OF FAILURE MODES

The transverse failure mode of the 0° samples consisted of microbuckling and kinking of the fibers. Kinking angles in 0° plies have also been reported to be in the range 10° to 20° [14,18]. However, the macroscopic fracture patterns of the quasi-isotropic laminates were brooming and shear. This suggests that failure initiates in the 0° plies by microbuckling but that the final failure modes were matrix shear crack propagation in the 90° plies (shear pattern) and delamination (brooming pattern). It appeared that the as-received samples exhibited no brooming component, whereas the samples cycled for three months at 25°C and 149°C both showed brooming. This suggests that internal delamination had already started after three months of testing, even though compressive failure strength is known to depend upon fixture geometry [18,19]. Microscopic examination to about 1500X did not reveal any signs of damage or edge delamination. The failure sequence and mechanisms were similar in both cyclic and static fatigue.

CORRELATION OF STIFFNESS REDUCTION WITH PLY STRESSES

Stresses arising in each ply for a given layup (A, B, C, or D) under static compressive loading help to identify which ply is likely to fail first in fatigue. This in turn helps to obtain a tentative time sequence of the various intralaminar failure modes, since a ply will tend to fail in a different mode depending on its orientation. This is a consistent approach since experiments have shown that intraply failures usually precede interlaminar failures such as delamination [14]. The highest compressive loads were calculated to occur in the 0° ply of the C laminate, followed by the A and B laminates and then the D laminate. The 0° plies, which are subjected to a compressive state of stress, will tend to fail by fiber microbuckling and fiber kinking. The 90° plies, subjected to a tensile state of stress, will tend to fail by matrix cracking and fiber debonding.

CORRELATION OF PLY STRENGTH RATIOS WITH RELATIVE STIFFNESS REDUCTION

Imposition of a compressive axial load of -76 MPa gave identical ply strains, stresses, R-factors, etc... for the quasi-A and quasi-B laminates. (R-factors are the ratio of allowable to actual stresses, and were calculated for either intact or for degraded plies using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion [20]). All laminates showed the lowest intact R-ratio in the 90° plies and the lowest degraded R-ratio in the 0° plies. This implies initial failure would be in the 90° plies, followed by failure in the 0° plies. The first ply failure ratios were -9.17 for A and B, -6.74

for C, and -12.3 for D. This suggests that the A and B laminates would have a higher stiffness reduction after a given time than the D laminate, which was not found to be the case. Thus the laminate where the 90° (axial) stresses were highest should show the most degradation. This model predicts successfully that the D laminate would be intermediate in degradation.

ANALYSIS OF INTERLAMINAR STRESSES

Interlaminar stresses were examined to see if delamination tendencies correlated with stiffness reduction. The free edges of a laminate give rise to interlaminar normal and shear stresses which are highly dependent upon stacking sequence and which may promote delamination during compression cycling. The laminate with the highest number of (+45°/-45°) interfaces and the lowest number of 0° plies displayed the largest stiffness decrease. This agreed with reports that (+45°/-45°) interfaces are detrimental to fatigue strength by initiating delamination [21]. We note however, that the stiffness of sample B decreased more slowly than that of sample A, even though B has four (+45°/-45°) interfaces and A has none. A possible explanation might be the position of the 0° plies, which are more susceptible to microbuckling for failure initiation when located nearer to the surface of the sample.

There are various schemes to predict the onset of delamination [16,17,22], including several that are based on classical laminate plate theory (CLPT). Apparent Poisson's ratios can be used as indicators of the interlaminar normal stresses (σ_z) which load to Mode I delamination [17]. These are important in cross ply laminates where interlaminar shear stresses, such as τ_{zx} , goes to zero. However, our laminates contain numerous 45° plies. In this case we examine effective shear coupling coefficients η (coefficients of mutual influence) [22]. Joo and Sun [23] showed that the average interlaminar shear stress can be approximated by:

$$\tau_{zx} = C' \epsilon_{xx} |\Delta\eta| \quad \text{where} \quad |\Delta\eta| = \alpha + k\beta, \quad k=1 \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} \alpha = \bar{\eta}_{xy,x}^{*1} - \bar{\eta}_{xy,x}^{*2} \\ \beta = \bar{\eta}_{xy,x}^1 - \bar{\eta}_{xy,x}^2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The indices 1, 2 refer to inner and outer layers and the superscript * and the bar refer to adjacent plies or sublaminates, respectively. Applying this analysis to the three or four outer interfaces of all the laminates, we find that the $\Delta\eta$ values are maximum for three first interfaces in the A, B, and C laminates, and the third interface (the 0°/-45° interface) in the D laminate. The values are -2.45, -2.358, -2.27, and -1.9, respectively. These are relatively low tendencies to delaminate [22,23] and one would not expect to find significant edge cracking, except possibly in the A laminate after prolonged cycling. For compressive loading, thermal and mechanical effects (γ_{xy}) are additive while in tensile loading they cancel out [22]. However, our testing was done at a comparatively high temperature (149°C), so combined stresses will not be significant for delamination propensity.

CONCLUSIONS

Correlation to the order of stiffness degradation during creep was best for the following parameters (Table 3). Most criteria, such as first ply failure, predicted the C laminate would show the greatest stiffness degradation. The laminate with the highest number of (+45°/-45°) interfaces and lowest number of 0° plies (quasi-C) displayed the largest stiffness decrease, in agreement with a model predicting that (+45°/-45°) interfaces initiate delamination and consequently macrobuckling [21]. However, rates of stiffness decrease (dE/dN) leveled off after about 250 cycles. The D laminate had the lowest propensity for delamination, and also the highest stress ratio but nevertheless showed intermediate stiffness degradation. The most isotropic laminates (A, B) showed the overall lowest ΔE , suggesting a detrimental interaction

Table 3. Parameter correlating with fatigue induced ΔE

Laminates	Quasi-C	Quasi-D	Quasi-A, Quasi-B
Observed ΔE	Maximum	Intermediate	Minimum
Axial stress on 90° plies	82.6 MPa	41.7 MPa	39.6 MPa
Axial laminate strain	-0.186	-0.216	-0.287
Number of 0° plies	2	8	4, 4
Number of +45°/-45° interfaces	6	0	0, 4
Lesser agreement:			
R-ratio for First Ply Failure	6.74	12.3	9.17
$ \Delta\eta $	2.27	1.9	2.45, 2.36

of damage modes in the less isotropic laminates. Alternatively, we conclude that the most isotropic laminates (A, B) have low crack propagation rates and thus are more damage resistant than less isotropic laminates (this is similar to results on tension fatigue of Gr/BMI [6]). Occasional initial increases in stiffness (during tension fatigue) were also observed by Poursartip *et al* [24] who suggested they might be due to shearing of the 45° plies. Stiffness increases are also caused by physical aging; hence more work in this area is suggested. It is also recommended that longer times and higher stress levels be used to verify the damage modes. This would promote accurate future life predictions.

REFERENCES

1. W.C. Hansen, K. Shenoy, E.G. Wolff, Residual strength of Graphite/BMI composites after long term cyclical compression. *ICCM/9 Proceedings*, vol.V, 524-531 (1993).
2. E.G. Wolff, W.C. Hansen, K. Shenoy, Prediction of creep strains during cyclical compression of composites. *Proc. VII Int. Congr. Exp. Mech. SEM*, vol.I, 178-182 (1992)
3. O. Allix, P. Ladevèze, E. Vittecoq, Modelling and identification of the mechanical behaviour of composite laminates in compression. *Comp. Sci. Tech.* **51**, 35-42 (1994).
4. E.G. Wolff & S.R. Tyagi, Compression cycling of multiple samples with controlled environments. Submitted to *Experimental Mechanics*.
5. P.A. Steiner *et al.*, Development of failure resistant bismaleimide/carbon composites. *SAMPE Journal*, 8-14 (March/April 1987).
6. X.J. Xian, C.L. Choi, Fatigue fracture behaviour of carbon-fiber-reinforced modified bismaleimide composites. *Composites Science and Technology* **52**, 93-98 (1994).
7. D.H. Allen, S.E. Groves, C.E. Harris, A cumulative damage model for continuous fiber composite laminates with matrix cracking and interply delaminations. *ASTM STP 972*, 57-80 (1988).
8. R. Talreja, Stiffness properties of composite laminates with matrix cracking and interior delamination. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics* **25** no.5/6, 751-762 (1986).
9. B.Y. Liu, L.B. Lessard, Fatigue and damage-tolerance analysis of composite laminates: stiffness loss, damage-modelling, and life prediction. *Comp. Sci. Tech.* **51**,43-51 (1994).
10. J.N. Yang *et al.*, A stiffness degradation model for graphite/epoxy laminates. *J. Composite Materials* **24**, 753-769 (1990).
11. L.J. Lee, K.E. Fu, J.N. Yang, Fatigue damages of composite laminates under service loading. *ICCM 9* vol.5,723-730 (1991).

12. S.M. Jessen, A. Plumtree, Continuum damage mechanics applied to cyclic behaviour of a glass fibre composite pultrusion. *Composites* **22** no.3, 181-190 (1991).
13. J. Varna & L. Berglund, Multiple transverse cracking and stiffness reduction in cross-ply laminates. *J. Composites Technology & Research* **13** no.2, 97-106 (1991).
14. C. Soutis, Measurement of the static compressive strength of carbon-fibre/epoxy laminates. *Composites Science and Technology* **42**, 373-392 (1991).
15. S.L. Bazhenov & V.V. Kozey, Compression fracture of unidirectional carbon fibre-reinforced plastics. *J. Materials Science* **26**, 6764-6776 (1991).
16. J.P. Komorowski *et al*, Edge effects on the compression dominated fatigue resistance of Graphite-Epoxy laminates. *ICCM/9 Proceedings*, vol.VI, 597-604 (1993).
17. S. Subramanian, K.L. Reifsnider, W.W. Stinchcomb, Prediction of delamination onset characteristics in laminated composites. *39th Int. SAMPE Symp. Proc.*, 1237-1249 (1994).
18. E.M. Odoms, D.F. Adams, Failure modes of unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite compression specimens. *Composites* **21** no.4, 290-296 (1990).
19. P.T. Curtis, J. Gates, C.G. Molyneux, An improved engineering test method for measurement of the compressive strength of unidirectional carbon fibre composites. *Composites* **22** no.5, 363-368 (1991).
20. P. Sjoblom, Genlam Code. *Think Composites* Dayton, OH (1989).
21. P.S. Chen and A. Elshiekh, Effect of lay-up on the mechanical properties of laminates. *38th Int. SAMPE Symposium*, 1152-1157 (10-13 May 1993).
22. C.T. Herakovich, On the relationship between engineering properties and delamination of composite materials. *J. Composite Materials* **15**, 336-348 (1981).
23. J.W. Joo, C.T. Sun, A failure criterion for laminates governed by free edge interlaminar shear stress. *J. Composite Materials* **26**, 1510-1522 (1992).
24. A. Poursartip, M.F. Ashby, P.W.R. Beaumont, The fatigue damage mechanics of a carbon fibre composite laminate: I-Development of the model. II-Life prediction. *Composites Science and Technology* **25**, 193-218, 283-299 (1986).